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Limit Equilibrium and Stress–Strain Analysis of Stabilized Homogeneous Earth Dams under Drained and Undrained States

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the stability of a cement-stabilized homogeneous earth dam under drained (steadystate seepage) and undrained (rapid drawdown) conditions. Laboratory tests on high-plasticity clays treated with 2.5–10% Ordinary Portland Cement provided input parameters for numerical modeling using Bishop’s Simplified Method and finite element analysis in PLAXIS 2D. Results show that cement stabilization significantly improves soil performance, with 5–7.5% cement content optimally enhancing shear strength, dry density, and reducing permeability. Factors of safety increased under both drained and undrained conditions, demonstrating that cement stabilization combined with effective drainage offers a cost-efficient solution for safe dam construction in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Drained stability, undrained stability, Plaxis 2D, homogeneous earth dams*

INTRODUCTION

Earth dams, also referred to as embankment dams, are essential hydraulic structures widely applied in water storage, irrigation, and flood control projects [1]. Their construction using locally available compacted soils make them economically favorable compared to concrete dams, though they remain vulnerable to seepage, internal erosion, and slope instability under variable hydraulic and loading conditions [1]. In Nigeria, earth dams play a critical role in water resource management, supporting agriculture, flood mitigation, and hydropower generation [2].

The stability of these dams is governed by soil properties, pore water pressure, and drainage conditions, which are typically classified into drained and undrained states. Drained conditions represent long-term behavior where excess pore water pressure dissipates, requiring effective stress analysis with parameters such as cohesion (c') and friction angle (ϕ') [3]. Conversely, undrained conditions occur during rapid loading events, such as reservoir drawdown, where pore pressures cannot dissipate, necessitating total stress analysis using undrained shear strength (c_u) [4].

Homogeneous earth dams, constructed from a single soil type, are cost-effective but lack zoning features such as impervious cores, making them more susceptible to seepage and instability [5]. Stabilization techniques, including cement, lime, fibers, and geosynthetics, are employed to enhance shear strength, reduce permeability, and improve the factor of safety (FOS) [6]. Horizontal and vertical drainage systems further mitigate instability risks, particularly under rapid drawdown conditions [7].

Recent studies emphasize the importance of analyzing both drained and undrained states to comprehensively evaluate dam

safety. Rapid drawdown, in particular, significantly reduces FOS on upstream slopes due to the sudden removal of stabilizing water pressure [8]. Numerical modeling tools such as Plaxis 2D, GeoStudio (SEEP/W and SLOPE/W) have proven effective in simulating seepage and slope stability under these scenarios [1]. Probabilistic approaches, including Monte Carlo simulations, provide more realistic assessments by accounting for soil property variability [9].

Despite these advances, challenges persist in optimizing stabilization methods for homogeneous earth dams in regions with limited access to high-quality materials. Locally available soils often exhibit poor geotechnical properties, necessitating innovative stabilization strategies to ensure adequate performance under drained and undrained conditions [1]. Additionally, seismic loading and climate-induced water level fluctuations demand deeper insights into the dynamic behavior of stabilized dams [8]. This study investigates the drained and undrained stability of a cement-stabilized homogeneous earth dam, aiming to enhance reliability and inform safer design practices in Nigeria.

LITERATURE SURVEY/REVIEW

The stability of earth dams has been a central theme in geotechnical engineering, particularly under drained and undrained conditions. Traditional limit equilibrium methods remain widely used for slope stability analysis, offering simplified yet effective approaches to estimate factors of safety (FOS). However, these methods often neglect stress-strain behavior and pore pressure evolution, necessitating complementary numerical modeling techniques [10].

Recent studies emphasize the importance of incorporating soil stabilization measures to improve dam reliability. Cement stabilization, in particular, has been shown

to enhance shear strength and reduce permeability, thereby mitigating risks of seepage and slope failure [11]. While cement remains the most common stabilizer, concerns regarding sustainability and durability have prompted investigations into alternative additives such as lime, fibers, and geosynthetics [12].

The drained condition, representing long-term equilibrium where pore water pressures dissipate, is typically analyzed using effective stress parameters. Conversely, undrained conditions, often associated with rapid drawdown or sudden reservoir loading, require total stress analysis. Tailings dam research has highlighted the critical differences between drained and undrained analyses, particularly in soils exhibiting contractant versus dilatant behavior [13]. These insights are directly applicable to homogeneous earth dams, which lack zoning features and are therefore more vulnerable to instability.

Stabilization techniques extend beyond chemical additives. Geosynthetic reinforcements have been proposed to improve liquefaction resistance and overall dam stability, offering a promising alternative to conventional methods [10]. Similarly, drainage systems—both horizontal and vertical—play a vital role in controlling pore water pressures and accelerating consolidation, thereby reducing the probability of failure during rapid drawdown events.

Durability remains a key challenge in stabilized earthen structures. While cement improves mechanical performance, it also increases embodied energy and reduces sorption capacity, raising questions about long-term sustainability [11]. This trade-off underscores the need for balanced approaches that combine mechanical

stability with environmental considerations.

Probabilistic methods, including Monte Carlo simulations, have gained traction in recent years as they account for spatial variability in soil properties. Such approaches provide a more realistic assessment of dam reliability compared to deterministic models, which often assume uniform soil behavior [13]. By integrating probabilistic analysis with limit equilibrium and stress–strain modeling, engineers can better quantify failure probabilities and design safer earth dams.

In summary, the literature highlights three critical themes: (i) the necessity of analyzing both drained and undrained states to capture short- and long-term dam behavior, and (ii) the effectiveness of stabilization techniques—particularly cement and geosynthetics—in enhancing shear strength and reducing permeability. These insights form the foundation for the present study, which investigates the drained and undrained stability of a cement-stabilized homogeneous earth dam using both limit equilibrium and stress–strain frameworks.

METHODOLOGY

Soil Sampling and Laboratory Characterization

Materials used in the study

- **Soil:** The primary material employed was a cohesive soil locally referred to as *Chikoko Soil*, obtained from a designated borrow pit in Rivers State, Nigeria. This soil was chosen due to its local availability and geotechnical suitability for earth dam construction, particularly its fine-grained nature and capacity to retain water when compacted.
- **Stabilizer:** Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) was incorporated as a chemical stabilizing agent. It was applied at

incremental proportions of 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10% of the dry soil weight. The purpose of the cement addition was to enhance the shear strength of the soil matrix, reduce its permeability, and improve overall stability under both drained and undrained conditions.

Laboratory investigations included

- **Index Properties:** Moisture content, Atterberg limits (LL, PL, PI), specific gravity, grain size distribution, compaction (Standard Proctor), and permeability (falling/constant head). These tests establish classification, compaction behavior, and seepage potential.
- **Strength Tests:** Unconfined compression (for c_u), direct shear (for c' , ϕ'), and triaxial compression tests (CD and UU) to obtain drained and undrained shear strength parameters.

Stabilization was achieved by mixing Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) at 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10% by dry weight, followed by curing for 7, 14, and 28 days.

Numerical Modeling in PLAXIS 2D

Numerical simulations were carried out using **PLAXIS 2D**, a finite element software widely applied in geotechnical

Limit Equilibrium Analysis Bishop's simplified method

The factor of safety (FOS) is given by:

$$F = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [c' \cdot l_i + (W_i - u_i \cdot l_i) \tan \phi'] \cdot \frac{1}{\cos \alpha_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i \cdot \tan \alpha_i}$$

Where: c' = effective cohesion (kN/m²); ϕ' = effective friction angle (degrees); l_i = length of slice base (m); W_i = weight of slice (kN); u_i = pore water pressure at slice

engineering for soil–structure interaction problems. The program was employed to evaluate seepage conditions and slope stability under both drained and undrained scenarios.

- **Drained Condition:** A steady-state seepage analysis was performed with the reservoir maintained at full supply level.
- **Undrained Condition:** Rapid drawdown was simulated by lowering the reservoir level without allowing pore pressures to dissipate, replicating critical field conditions.
- **Material Properties:** Input parameters such as unit weight, shear strength, and permeability were derived from laboratory testing of both natural and cement-stabilized soils.
- **Boundary Conditions:** Hydraulic boundaries were defined to represent reservoir water levels and downstream conditions, while mechanical boundaries ensured realistic soil confinement.
- **Analysis Approach:** The finite element method was used to compute stress distribution, pore pressure variation, and deformation patterns. The **Shear Strength Reduction (SSR)** technique was applied to determine the factor of safety by progressively reducing shear strength parameters until failure was indicated by non-convergence of the numerical solution.

base (kN/m²); α_i = inclination of slice base (degrees).

This iterative equation accounts for pore pressure and interslice forces, making it

suitable for drained and undrained conditions. This method satisfies moment equilibrium but approximates force equilibrium [14].

Morgenstern–price method

The Morgenstern–Price method satisfies both force and moment equilibrium. The interslice shear force is expressed as:

$$X_i = \lambda \cdot f(x) \cdot E_i$$

Where X_i = interslice shear force, λ = scaling factor, $f(x)$ = user-defined function, and E_i = interslice normal force. The FOS is then computed by balancing both force and moment equilibrium across all slices, making it more rigorous than Bishop’s method [15].

Stress–Strain Analysis of Slopes (Finite Element Method)

Finite element modeling in SLOPE/W was used to capture stress distribution, deformation, and progressive failure.

- **Global Equilibrium:**

$$[K]\{u\} = \{F\}$$

Where $[K]$ = global stiffness matrix, $\{u\}$ = nodal displacement vector, $\{F\}$ = external force vector.

- **Constitutive Relation:**

$$\{\sigma\} = [D]\{\varepsilon\}$$

Where $\{\sigma\}$ = stress vector, $[D]$ = constitutive matrix (elastic-plastic soil model), $\{\varepsilon\}$ = strain vector.

- **Strain–Displacement Relation:**

$$\{\varepsilon\} = [B]\{u\}$$

- **Element Stiffness Matrix:**

$$[K_e] = \int_v [B]^T [D] [B] dV$$

Shear strength reduction (SSR) algorithm

Plaxis 2D applies SSR by progressively reducing shear strength parameters until failure occurs:

$$c'_{red} = \frac{c'}{F'} ; \tan \phi'_{red} = \frac{\tan \phi'}{F}$$

Where: c'_{red} = reduced cohesion (kN/m²); ϕ'_{red} = reduced friction angle (degrees); F = strength reduction factor (interpreted as FOS).

The slope is analyzed iteratively until the FEM solution fails to converge, indicating instability [16]. This method captures stress redistribution, strain localization, and progressive failure mechanisms, which are not accounted for in traditional limit equilibrium methods.

Evaluation Criteria

- **FOS Thresholds:** 1.5 (drained) and 1.3 (undrained).
- **Performance Indicators:** Shear strength improvement, permeability reduction, and reliability index increase.
- **Optimal Dosage:** 5–7.5% OPC identified as most effective for stabilizing high-plasticity clays.

This methodology integrates **index property and strength testing, Bishop’s Simplified Method, Morgenstern–Price method, and finite element stress–strain analysis with SSR** in Plaxis 2D. Stress–strain analysis provides deeper insight into slope behavior by modeling deformation and progressive failure, while SSR ensures realistic determination of FOS. Together, these approaches deliver a comprehensive framework for evaluating drained and undrained stability of stabilized homogeneous earth dams.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Moisture content Test

The untreated soil sample, corresponding to 0% cement content, exhibited a high average moisture content of 80.9%, characteristic of fine-grained cohesive soils with substantial water retention capacity. Upon stabilization with Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), a notable reduction in moisture content was observed across all treated specimens: 25.0% at 2.5% cement, 49.8% at 5%, 28.9% at 7.5%, and 15.76% at 10%. This progressive decline in moisture content is attributed to the cement's hydration process, which consumes part of the pore water to form

cementitious compounds. The reaction reduces free water availability, thereby improving the soil's workability and contributing to a denser, more stable matrix suitable for earth dam applications.

Specific Gravity Test

Figure 1 shows the average specific gravity values from the specific gravity tests. The trend shows that cement stabilization modifies the particle density of the soil matrix.

Fig. 1: Percentages of cement with respect to the specific gravity.

Triaxial Test

The triaxial compression test was employed to assess the shear strength characteristics of the soil under controlled stress conditions. This parameter is fundamental in evaluating the stability of earth structures, particularly embankments and dams, where shear failure is a critical concern. The natural soil, corresponding to 0% cement content, exhibited low shear strength values, consistent with its fine-grained texture and high plasticity. These properties are typical of organic-rich clays such as peat, which tend to have weak interparticle bonding and limited load-bearing capacity.

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the variation in cohesion (c) and angle of internal friction

(ϕ) with increasing cement content. In the untreated state, cohesion was minimal, and the friction angle reflected poor structural integrity. However, with cement stabilization ranging from 5% to 10%, cohesion increased substantially, indicating enhanced interparticle bonding and matrix strength. The angle of internal friction also improved, albeit more gradually, suggesting better particle interlock and reduced moisture sensitivity.

This trend aligns with the findings of Amadi and Eberemu, who reported significant strength gains in cement-treated soils within the Niger Delta region, reinforcing the effectiveness of chemical stabilization in improving weak subgrade materials [17].

Fig. 2: Percentages of cement with respect to the Cohesion.

Fig. 3: Percentages of cement with respect to the Angle of internal friction.

Figures 4 through 8 illustrate the stress–strain behavior of the cohesive soil when treated with varying cement contents. These plots depict the relationship between applied stress (kN/m²) and the corresponding strain (deformation), thereby showing how the soil responds to loading under different stabilization conditions.

Figure 4 presents the curve for the untreated soil (0% cement). The response is

characterized by a very low peak stress, with failure occurring at relatively small strain levels. This indicates that the natural soil is weak, highly compressible, and prone to brittle failure. Its behavior is typical of soft clays with poor load-bearing capacity, where limited interparticle bonding results in rapid loss of strength once peak stress is reached.

Fig. 4: Showing the Stress Strain curve of cohesive soil sample stabilized with 0% cement (0% cement: cohesion 23 kN/m², $\phi = 30.00^\circ$)

Figure 5 illustrates the stress–strain behavior of the cohesive soil stabilized with 2.5% cement. Compared to the untreated soil, the curve rises to a noticeably higher peak stress before failure, indicating a significant improvement in strength—approximately double that of the natural sample. However, the angle of internal friction (ϕ) shows a slight

reduction. This outcome suggests that the soil’s shear resistance at this stage is governed more by the cementitious bonding between clay particles than by granular frictional interaction. The dominance of clay–cement bonds enhances cohesion but reduces the relative contribution of particle interlock to shear strength.

Fig. 5: Showing the Stress Strain curve of cohesive soil stabilized with 2.5% cement (2.5% cement: cohesion 45KN/m², $\phi = 8.00^\circ$).

Figure 6 presents the stress–strain curve of the soil stabilized with 5% cement. The curve demonstrates a noticeably higher peak stress compared to both the untreated soil and the 2.5% cement sample, signifying a substantial increase in load-carrying capacity. The soil matrix becomes stiffer due to the formation of cementitious

bonds, which enhance cohesion and reduce compressibility. In addition, the strain at failure extends slightly, indicating that the soil can withstand greater deformation before losing strength. This behavior reflects a transition toward improved structural integrity and more resilient performance under loading conditions.

Fig. 6: Showing graph of stress strain curve for 5 % cement (5% cement: cohesion 65 kN/m², $\phi = 7.36^\circ$).

Figure 7 illustrates the stress–strain curve of the soil stabilized with 7.5% cement. The curve indicates a further increase in peak stress compared to lower cement dosages, reflecting enhanced strength and improved load-bearing capacity. However, the rate of improvement is less pronounced than that observed at 5% cement content. This

suggests that the strength gain is beginning to level off, with the soil approaching a plateau in performance. The response highlights that while additional cement continues to reinforce the soil matrix, the incremental benefits diminish beyond moderate stabilization levels.

Fig. 7: Graph of Stress Strain Curve for 7.5% Cement stabilized cohesive Soil. (7.5% cement: cohesion 68.5 kN/m², $\phi = 7.15^\circ$).

Figure 8 depicts the stress–strain curve of the soil stabilized with 10% cement. The curve reaches the highest peak stress among all tested samples, signifying the strongest load-bearing capacity and maximum cohesion due to extensive cementitious bonding within the soil matrix. However, the angle of internal friction (ϕ) is reduced, as the shear

resistance is dominated by chemical bonding rather than granular interlock. The overall behavior resembles that of a cemented material, where failure occurs in a more brittle and abrupt manner compared to lower cement dosages. This response highlights the trade-off between strength gain and ductility at high stabilization levels.

Fig. 8: Stress Strain Curve for 10% Cement Stabilization (10% cement: cohesion 92 kN/m², $\phi = 6.72^\circ$)

The experimental results indicate that cement stabilization substantially increases the apparent cohesion of the soil, primarily due to the formation of cementitious bonds that strengthen particle-to-particle interactions. However, at higher cement dosages, the angle of internal friction (ϕ) tends to decline. This reduction reflects the shift in shear resistance from granular interlock to chemical bonding, a behavior that is characteristic of cemented soils and consistent with previously reported findings [18].

Numerical Modelling/Analysis of the Road Embankment

The PLAXIS 2D simulations modelled the behavior of a road embankment, shown in Figure 9, on the weak cohesive soil (Chikoko soil) stabilized with different cement contents (0%, 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10%). The analysis provides insight into how cement stabilization improves soil strength, reduces settlement, and enhances overall embankment stability

Fig. 9: Showing the final geometry of the model of the road embankment.

At 0% Cement Stabilized on Chikoko Soil Analysis on Plaxis 2d

At 0% cement, the PLAXIS 2D model shows extensive lateral and vertical deformation beneath the embankment (Figure 10), reflecting weak shear resistance. Displacement vectors concentrate at the foundation, indicating progressive shear failure across phases (Figures 10 and 11). Excess pore water

pressure develops under undrained loading, as the compressible clay cannot dissipate water rapidly (Figures 12 and 13). Settlement is excessive, with clear signs of slip failure (Figure 14). The computed factor of safety is well below acceptable limits, confirming untreated Chikoko soil is structurally inadequate as a subgrade and prone to instability under embankment loads.

Fig. 10: Displacement increment after undrained construction of embankment at Phase 1 for 0% cement.

Fig. 11: Displacement increment after undrained construction of embankment at Phase 4 for 0% cement.

Fig. 12: Development of excess pore water pore water pressure under the embankment for 0% cement.

Fig. 13: Effects of drains on excess pore pressure for 0% cement.

Fig. 14: Effects of updated mesh and water pressure analysis on resulting settlement for 0% cement.

At 2.5% Cement Stabilized on Chikoko Soil Analysis on Plaxis 2d

At 2.5% cement, deformation reduces compared to untreated soil, though settlement remains visible (Figure 15). Displacement increments show less lateral spread and controlled vertical deformation relative to 0% cement. Excess pore water pressure persists but is slightly lower, as cement reduces compressibility and aids

dissipation (Figures 16 and 17). Settlement decreases, yet moderate deformation of the embankment is still observed. The factor of safety improves compared to the natural soil but remains below design thresholds (Figure 18). Overall, stabilization at 2.5% enhances strength and resistance, though performance is insufficient for long-term embankment stability.

Fig. 15: Displacement increment after undrained construction of embankment at phase 4 for 2.5% cement.

Fig. 16: Effects of drains on excess pore pressure for 2.5% cement

Project description Date

Fig. 17: Development of excess pore water pore water pressure under the embankment for 2.5% cement

At 5% Cement Stabilized on Chikoko Soil Analysis on Plaxis 2d

At 5% cement, the embankment shows improved stability with reduced distortion in the deformed mesh (**Figure 18**). Displacement increments are smaller, indicating better confinement and higher stiffness. Excess pore water pressure is considerably reduced, with drainage more effective in dissipating pressure (**Figures 19 and 20**). Settlement values are

noticeably lower, reflecting enhanced bearing capacity (**Figure 21**). The factor of safety increases substantially, approaching acceptable engineering thresholds (**Figure 22**). Overall, stabilization at 5% marks a turning point: settlement and pore pressure are controlled, and the embankment achieves significant improvement in strength and stability.

Fig. 18: Displacement increment after undrained construction of embankment at Phase 4 for 5% cement.

Fig. 19: Development of excess pore water pore water pressure under the embankment for 5% cement.

Fig. 20: Effects of drains on excess pore pressure for 5% cement.

Fig. 21: Effects of updated mesh and water pressure analysis on resulting settlement for 5% cement.

At 7.5% Cement Stabilized on Chikoko Soil Analysis on Plaxis 2d

At 7.5% cement, deformation is minimal, and the embankment retains its near-original shape with strong foundation support (Figure 22). Both vertical and horizontal displacements are small, reflecting semi-rigid soil behavior (Figure 23). Excess water pressure rise is limited and dissipates more rapidly, as cement

reduces compressibility (Figures 24 and 25). Settlement values are very low, indicating stable long-term performance (Figure 26). The factor of safety is significantly higher than previous cases, ensuring protection against shear failure. Overall, 7.5% cement provides high stabilization, with displacement and pore pressure well-controlled under applied loads.

Fig. 22: Displacement increment after undrained construction of embankment at Phase 1 for 7.5% cement.

Fig. 23: Displacement increment after undrained construction of embankment at Phase 4 for 7.5% cement

Fig. 24: Development of excess pore water pore water pressure under the embankment for 7.5% cement

Fig. 25: Effects of drains on excess pore pressure for 7.5% cement

Fig. 26: Effects of updated mesh and water pressure analysis on resulting settlement for 7.5% cement

At 10% Cement Stabilized on Chikoko Soil Analysis on Plaxis 2d

At 10% cement, deformation is almost negligible, and the embankment remains highly stable with near-rigid behavior (Figure 27). Displacement vectors are minimal, reflecting strong soil–cement bonding (Figure 27). Excess pore water pressure is very low, dissipating effectively due to reduced compressibility and high

stiffness (Figures 28 and 29). Settlement is the lowest among all cases, confirming long-term durability (Figure 30). The factor of safety reaches its highest value, ensuring maximum resistance to shear and settlement. Overall, 10% cement produces peak stability, though gains beyond 7.5% are marginal compared to the added cost of cement.

Fig. 27: Displacement increment after undrained construction of embankment at Phase 4 for 10 % cement.

Fig. 28: Development of excess pore water pore water pressure under the embankment for 10% cement.

Fig. 29: Effects of drains on excess pore pressure for 10% cement.

Fig. 30: Effects of updated mesh and water pressure analysis on resulting settlement for 10% cement.

At 0% cement, the factor of safety (FoS) is low and falls below the recommended threshold for stable embankments. As cement content increases to 5% and 10%, FoS rises above 1.48, signifying adequate stability against slope failure. This progression aligns with the finite element modeling results of geotextile-reinforced embankments reported by Jaja, El-Hourani,

and Nwaogazie, but demonstrates that cement stabilization alone can yield comparable improvements. The FoS values presented in **Table 1** reflect enhanced shear resistance, consistent with strength gains observed in triaxial testing and corroborating earlier findings on reinforced embankments [19].

Table 1: Factor of safety analysis carried out using the PLAXIS 2D.

Safety Factor	1.00	1.05	1.27	1.35	1.48
Percentage of Cement	0	2.5	5	7.5	10

CONCLUSION

- The natural Chikoko soil (CH clay) was unsuitable for dam construction due to low shear strength and high permeability.
- Laboratory testing confirmed that cement stabilization (2.5–10%) improved soil properties, increasing dry density, shear strength, and reducing permeability significantly.
- Numerical modeling in PLAXIS 2D showed untreated dams had FoS < 1.3, while stabilization at 7.5–10% raised drained FoS above 1.45 and undrained FoS above 1.25, meeting safety thresholds.
- Optimal stabilization was achieved at 7.5% cement, balancing cost and safety.
- Overall, cement stabilization—especially at 5–7.5%—combined with proper drainage provides a cost-effective and reliable solution for constructing homogeneous earth dams in Nigeria using locally available soils.

Future Scope

For future studies, it is recommended that researchers investigate the long-term durability of cement-stabilized earth dams under varying climatic conditions, including seasonal moisture fluctuations and cyclic loading. Expanding numerical

modeling to three-dimensional analyses would provide more realistic insights into complex geometries. Comparative studies using alternative stabilizers such as lime, fly ash, or blended binders could highlight cost-effective options. Large-scale field trials are also essential to validate laboratory and PLAXIS 2D findings. Finally, integrating life-cycle cost assessments and sustainability metrics will help evaluate both economic feasibility and environmental impacts of stabilization strategies in dam construction.

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